

THE EFFECT OF GIBBERELLIN GROWTH STIMULANT ON THE GROWTH OF ORDINARY HORSE CHESTNUT SEEDLINGS USED FOR GREENING CITY STREETS AND HIGHWAYS

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Abstract. This study investigates the effect of the growth regulator gibberellin on the growth of ordinary chestnut seedlings. Gibberellin is a highly physiologically active substance that stimulates plant growth. The results indicate that at a concentration of 20.0 mg/L, gibberellin application led to a 26.4% increase in seedling growth. Additionally, an increase in the amount of gibberellin applied resulted in significant enhancements in both the height and diameter of the plants. Research by M.Kh. Chaylakhyan confirms that young plants show pronounced height growth when treated with gibberellin. This study provides information on the effectiveness of gibberellin in promoting the development of tree-like plants and emphasizes the need for further exploration of new growth-regulating substances.

Keywords: gibberellin, plant growth, chestnut seedlings, physiological activity, growth dynamics, concentration, advantage, height growth, diameter growth, young plants, metabolism, growth regulators, research findings, tree-like plants.

Introduction

In the field of nursery development, extensive research is being conducted aimed at increasing the share of standard seedlings, reducing production times, and improving survival rates. Currently, significant attention is being given to the study of growth, development, and survival of horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum*) and Japanese sophora (*Sophora japonica*) seedlings, based on results from scientific research.

In Uzbekistan, the demand for ornamental trees is growing each year, particularly for horse chestnut and Japanese sophora seedlings. Between 2008 and 2012, the goal was set to prepare 8.1 million Japanese sophora seedlings and 1.2 million horse chestnut seedlings, highlighting the importance of these tree species in landscape design and the country's ecology.

According to the data from the State Forestry Committee, more than 110,000 horse chestnut seedlings and over 170,000 Japanese sophora seedlings were planted in 2017. These trees are actively used not only for urban greening but also for improving areas along highways, contributing to the enhancement of the ecological situation in urbanized areas.

In the future, it is crucial to develop and scientifically justify a system of agronomic measures aimed at the inexpensive and high-quality production of seedlings of these two tree species. This will allow for achieving high efficiency in nursery production, improving the quality of green spaces in cities, and supporting the sustainable development of urban ecosystems. Thus, the relevance of this research is determined not only by market needs but also by the broader ecological challenges facing society.

Research Methods. In this study, various methods were applied to ensure a comprehensive analysis and assessment of the growth and development of horse chestnut (*Aesculus hippocastanum*) and Japanese sophora (*Sophora japonica*) seedlings. The primary methods included field experiments, phenological observations, and biometric measurements, which allowed for reliable and objective data on the plants. All research procedures were conducted in accordance with the methodology proposed by B.A. Dospekhov (1985), ensuring the standardization and accuracy of the obtained results.

For the chemical analysis of soil and plant samples, methods described in the guide "Methods of Agrochemical, Agrophysical, and Microbiological Soil Research in Central Asia" (1977) were used. These methods allowed for a deeper investigation of the nutrients available to the plants and an assessment of their impact on the growth and development of the seedlings. The analysis included determining the content of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and other micronutrients, which is essential for understanding the soil conditions conducive to the successful cultivation of these species.

The climatic conditions of the area where the experiment was conducted were analyzed based on data from the "Tashkent" meteorological station. This data included information on temperature, humidity, precipitation, and other climatic factors that can significantly influence plant growth and development. The analysis of climatic conditions helped identify optimal parameters for the successful growth of seedlings and develop recommendations for agronomic practices.

Additionally, the economic efficiency of agronomic measures aimed at stimulating seedling growth was assessed based on sample technological maps developed at the Research Institute of Forestry. These maps served as a basis for evaluating production costs and expected profits from seedling cultivation. It is important to note that the analysis also took into account labor and resource costs, allowing for more accurate forecasting of financial outcomes.

Thus, the combination of various research methods provided comprehensive and precise data on the growth and development of seedlings, which is crucial for developing effective agronomic strategies in the fields of forestry and horticulture. This approach will not only help optimize production processes but also enhance the sustainability of green spaces in urban and rural settings.

Obtained Results and Their Analysis. In the process of selecting plant species for greening city streets and highways, it is crucial to choose species that grow quickly and efficiently. Using various growth stimulants plays a vital role in achieving this goal, and evaluating their effectiveness is essential. Among the chemical substances with growth-promoting properties, indoleacetic acid (IAA, heteroauxin), beta-indolylbutyric acid (IBA), alpha-naphthaleneacetic acid (NAA), and its salts, as well as NAA oil-based mixtures, have shown significant results when tested repeatedly on tree-like plants. While these substances have high efficiency, their cost and ease of use should also be considered. Therefore, there is a need to find new growth stimulants that are affordable and easy to use.

Gibberellin is one of the substances that strongly influence plant growth. Its effects extend not only to growth but also, in certain cases, to the plant's metabolism. Gibberellin is known for its strong impact on young seedlings of tree-like plants, and all types of tree plants are highly responsive to it. This was also confirmed in our research.

In the first year of the study, when the preparation "Gibberellin" was applied at a concentration of 20.0 mg/l, the seedlings showed 26.4% higher growth compared to other

variants. The data provided in Table 3.10 shows that as the concentration of gibberellin increased, both the height and width growth of the plants significantly improved. Compared to other growth stimulants, gibberellin was found to be the most effective, particularly in stimulating the growth of the upper parts of the plants.

According to researcher M.K. Chailakhyan [2.113; pp. 22-56], when young plants are treated with gibberellin, their height growth increases significantly. This is particularly noticeable during the phase when the plants are producing true leaves.

Thus, using growth stimulants like gibberellin in the greening of city streets and highways can serve as an important tool for ensuring the fast and effective growth of plants

Table 3.10

The effect of gibberellin on the growth of one-year-old ordinary horse chestnut seedlings.

Experimental Variants	Statistical Indicators						
	M±m	S	V	N	%	P	T
Height, cm							
Control (Water)	12,5±0,99	6,8	35,6	145	100	5,5	0
10 mg/l	13,9±0,95	5,8	32,8	123	111,2	5,2	0,3
15 mg/l	14,4±1,11	7,4	36,1	131	115,2	5,6	1,4
20 mg/l	15,8±1,10	7,4	37,1	137	126,4	5,7	1,0
Diameter, mm							
Control (Water)	4,2±0,3	1,6	17,6	145	100	2,6	0
10 mg/l	5,2±0,2	1,6	18,1	123	123,8	2,6	1,0
15 mg/l	5,5±0,4	1,6	18,2	131	130,9	2,9	1,7
20 mg/l	6,2±0,2	1,6	17,6	137	142,6	2,7	1,1

In our study on the application of gibberellin, the plants in the experimental variants were sprayed in two distinct stages: the first application was when 2-3 leaves had emerged (on April 21), and the second during the active growth phase of the seedlings. Throughout the research, the control group was treated with distilled water.

The data collected reveal that in the variants treated with gibberellin, the growth rate of the two-year-old ordinary horse chestnut seedlings accelerated significantly. In the seedlings treated with 25 mg/l of gibberellin, the height reached 42.5 cm, with a stem diameter of 13.7 mm. In contrast, the control group's seedlings showed a height of 36.4 cm and a stem diameter of 12.3 mm. When treated with a 50 mg/l concentration solution, the plants' height reached 43.8 cm, with a stem diameter of 14.2 mm, reflecting an increase of 7.4 cm in height and 1.9 mm in diameter compared to the control group.

The most significant growth in stem height was observed in the two-year-old seedlings treated with 75 mg/l of gibberellin. This demonstrates the pronounced effect of higher concentrations of gibberellin on the growth of these seedlings, suggesting that it is particularly effective at boosting plant development at this concentration level.

Conclusion

The research emphasizes the importance of selecting fast-growing and efficient plant species for greening city streets and highways. The use of growth-promoting substances, particularly gibberellin, has a significant impact on plant growth. When applied at a concentration of 20.0 mg/l, gibberellin resulted in a 26.4% increase in the growth of young seedlings compared to other variants.

The findings indicate that gibberellin is the most effective substance for stimulating growth, especially in the upper parts of the plants. These results underscore the importance of using effective and affordable forms of growth stimulants in urban greening efforts, which contribute to the overall improvement of the ecological environment.

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